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**2Integrated assessment of infant exposure to persistent organic
3pollutants and mercury via dietary intake in a central western
4Mediterranean site (Menorca Island)**

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23 Abstract

24 In this research the levels of organochlorine compounds (OCs) and mercury (Hg) in
25 several food items from Menorca Island were presented. The dietary exposure
26 assessment was performed in children population from the island. Finally, body burden
27 of OCs and Hg in these infants were associated with their dietary intakes of the selected
28 food items.

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30 The dietary exposure to persistent pollutants by children population from Menorca
31 Island was assessed. The concentrations of 11 organochlorine pesticides, 6
32 polychlorinated biphenils (PCBs) and 1 inorganic toxic element, Hg, were determined
33 in 46 food samples that included fish, shellfish, meat, fruit, vegetables, cheese and eggs,
34 which were acquired in local markets and department stores in the Menorca Island. The
35 most contaminated food items were fish and shellfish, followed by meat and cheese
36 products. OC levels were similar or lower than in other previous studies. However, 66
37 % of the analysed fish and shellfish species for Hg exceeded the human consumption
38 safety limits according to the European Union Legislation. Pollutant data from food was
39 combined with the pattern of consumption of these foodstuffs in order to calculate the
40 estimated daily intake (EDI) of these contaminants. According to our results, fish and
41 fruit were the main sources of OCs to the EDIs (contributing to 37 % and 29 %,
42 respectively) while fish and shellfish were the main sources of Hg (76 % and 17 %).
43 The estimated EDIs of OCs were well below to the reported FAO/WHO Tolerable
44 Intakes. However, estimated weekly intake of Hg would exceed the Provisional
45 Tolerable Weekly Intake indicated by EFSA in the case that the only fish and seafood
46 source would be from the central western Mediterranean. Direct associations between
47 fish/shellfish consumption and hair concentrations of Hg and fish and meat
48 consumption and 4,4'-DDT concentrations in venous serum in the Menorcan children
49 were observed.

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51 **Keywords:** Organochlorine compounds, Mercury, Food, Dietary exposure, Menorca
52 Island

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551. Introduction

56

57Anthropogenic release of organochlorine compounds (OCs) and mercury (Hg) into the
58environment has led to negative effects in human beings and ecosystems (Saeedi et al.,
592016, Lamborg et al., 2014). The OCs are synthetic products widely used since the
601920s for several applications. Some organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) were
61extensively used in agriculture due to their insecticidal and fungicidal properties.
62Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) were used for a large number of industrial
63applications, such as dielectrics in transformers, coatings, paints and insulating fluids
64(Wurl et al., 2005).

65 On the other hand, the environmental occurrence of Hg has been enhanced by
66mining and fossil fuel combustion (Lamborg et al., 2014). Hg is present in many
67chemical forms, being methylHg more toxic than the original metal. In the aquatic
68environment, Hg is readily transformed to methylHg by anaerobic bacteria. Most of the
69metal incorporated into aquatic organisms is in the methylated form (80-90%; Harris et
70al., 2003).

71 Human exposure to OCs has been related to several health effects including
72cancer, reproductive defects, neurobehavioral abnormalities and endocrine and
73immunological toxicity (Mrema et al., 2013). On the other hand, methylHg is a potent
74neurotoxic agent that can cause severe neurological damage to humans (Grandjean et
75al., 1997).

76 Despite their different origin and structure, OCs and Hg share common
77properties such as (I) strong chemical stability and environmental persistence, (II)
78bioconcentration in living organisms and biomagnification through the food chain due
79to their hydrophobic character and (III) toxicity for humans and wild animals.
80Accordingly, the production and use of OCs and Hg has been restricted and/or banned
81in many countries. However, these contaminants are still found in the environmental
82compartments (Arellano et al., 2011; Lamborg et al., 2014), foodstuff (Martí-Cid et al.,
832010; Olmedo et al., 2010) and human tissues (Vizcaino et al., 2014; Garí et al., 2013).

84 Dietary intake is a major way of incorporation of these compounds into humans.
85This is particularly important for children since their organs and metabolism are still
86under formation and pollutant exposure may have stronger long term effects than in
87adults (Guxens et al., 2012; Vizcaino et al., 2014).

88 Assessment of the main routes of exposure to these chemicals in infant
89populations is needed for implementation of adequate strategies towards minimization
90of pollutant intake. Previous studies have investigated the main routes of exposure to
91OCs (Leontjew et al., 2016, Ahmad et al., 2010, Stefanelli et al., 2004) or Hg (Rubio et
92al., 2016, Olmedo et al., 2013, Millour et al., 2011) but to the best of our knowledge
93none of them has performed integrated assessments on both types of pollutants in the
94same cohort. Concerning the OCs, the present study encompasses both PCBs and OCPs.

95 Menorca Island is located in the central Western Mediterranean (39°47' -
9640°05'N, 3°47' - 4°19'E) and has an extension of 702 Km². This small island represents
97a relatively isolated Mediterranean environment in which a large proportion of the food
98consumed by the inhabitants is generated locally. Furthermore, most of the fish
99consumption depends on the captures by local fishermen. The island has not any
100industry involving Hg use or production of OCs. Until the emergence of tourism, the
101main economic activity was agriculture. This island constitutes a representative case of
102a population living in a Mediterranean environment. High Hg levels are observed in the
103food-web of this semi-enclosed sea (Cossa et al., 1997; Gagnon et al., 1997; Pirrone et
104al., 2003; Heimbürger et al., 2010; Zagar et al., 2007) despite its anti-estuarine
105circulation pattern that transfers nutrients and pollutants to the Atlantic Ocean.
106Identification of the routes of transport of this metal and other pollutants into the
107population living in sites under Mediterranean influence is important. Menorca can be
108taken as a model ecosystem of communities living in marine Mediterranean
109environments in which the main routes of dietary pollutant incorporation of OC and Hg
110can be assessed.

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1132. Materials and methods

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1152.1. Sampling

116Food samples were acquired in local markets and department stores from the main two
117cities: Maó and Ciutadella (Fig 1; December 2014, n = 46). The selection was based on
118Food Frequency Questionnaires (FFQs) from 4 year old children from Menorca cohort
119(see next subsection below) and interviews with local experts.

120 The food samples included fish species of several trophic levels and fat contents
121(Table 1) and shellfish (Table 2), all them captured in the island surroundings. These

122 fish species were representative of the local consumption, encompassing angler
123 (*Lophius piscatorius*), European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), black seabream
124 (*Spondylisoma cantharus*), common dentex (*Dentex dentex*), common pandora
125 (*Pagellus erythrinus*), common seabream (*Pagrus pagrus*), dusky grouper (*Epinephelus*
126 *marginatus*), forkbeard (*Phycis phycis*), Mediterranean moray (*Muraena helena*), red
127 scorpionfish (*Scorpaena scrofa*), small-spotted catshark (*Scyliorhinus canicula*),
128 thornback ray (*Raja clavata*), red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*), red sea bream (*Pagellus*
129 *acarne*) and surmullet (*Mullus surmuletus*). The selected shellfish species were mussel
130 (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), squid (*Loligo vulgaris*), scampi (*Nephrops norvegicus*) and
131 shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*).

132 The food samples examined also included meat, e.g. beef, chicken and lamb
133 (Table 2), fruits and vegetables (Table 3), cheese (Table 3) and chicken eggs (Table 3),
134 all them produced locally.

135 After collection, each food item was dissected in two composite samples for OC
136 and Hg analyses. The former were wrapped in aluminium foil and the second were
137 sealed in plastic bags. The samples were then frozen at -23°C until further analysis in
138 the laboratory. Only the edible parts of each food item were analysed.

139

140 2.2. Study population

141 The Menorca cohort is part of the INMA (Spanish Children's Health and Environment)
142 project, a research network that focuses on the effects of environmental contaminants
143 during pregnancy and on fetal and child development (Ribas-Fitó et al., 2006; Guxens et
144 al., 2012).

145 Between 2001 and 2002, 4-year old children from this cohort provided serum
146 samples (n=285) and hair samples (n=302) for the determination of OCs and Hg,
147 respectively. These data have been described in Carrizo et al. (2006) and Garí et al.
148 (2013), respectively. Children's dietary intakes were assessed through FFQs (Vioque et
149 al., 1991; Willet et al., 1985). Only the dietary intakes which concurred with the
150 analysed food items were selected for study, as follows: fish, shellfish, meat (beef and
151 chicken), fruit, vegetables, cheese (semi-skimmed cheese) and eggs. The rest of food
152 items (e.g. dairy products, cereals, fats) were not included in the analyses.

153 All child's parents gave written permission for participation in the study, which
154 was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institut Municipal d'Investigació Mèdica
155 (Barcelona).

1572.3. *Chemicals and standards*

158 Solvents for residue analysis, *n*-hexane, dichloromethane, isooctane, acetone,
159 concentrated 95-97% sulphuric acid, 65% nitric acid, 30% hydrogen peroxide,
160 anhydrous sodium sulphate and silica gel were from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).
161 Sulphate and silica were activated overnight by heating at 400°C. The cellulose
162 extraction cartridges (22 mm x 80 mm) were from Whatman International Ltd. (UK).
163 Standard digestion teflon vessels (60 mL) were from Savillex (Minnesota, USA).
164 Standards of OCPs and PCB congeners were from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Wesel, Germany).
165 1,2,4,5-Tetrabromobenzene (TBB; Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) and PCB 209 (Dr.
166 Ehrenstorfer, Wesel, Germany) were used as recovery standards. PCB 142 (Dr.
167 Ehrenstorfer) was used as internal standard. The standard mixtures of OCPs, PCB and a
168 surrogate solution composed of TBB and PCB 209 were prepared in isooctane. Fish
169 muscle certified reference material, ERM-BB422, was obtained from the Institute for
170 Reference Materials and Measurements (Geel, Belgium).

171 The following pollutants were included in the analyses: pentachlorobenzene,
172 hexachlorobenzene (HCB), 4 isomers of hexachlorocyclohexane (α -, β -, γ - and δ -HCH),
173 2,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE, 2,4'-DDE and 4,4'-DDD, the ICES PCB congeners (28,
174 52, 101, 118, 138, 153 and 180) and total Hg.

175

1762.4. *Extraction and clean-up*

177 The methods of extraction and clean-up of OCs in fish, meat, vegetables and fruits were
178 based on previous analytical procedures (Berdie et al., 1998, Vives et al., 2002). Briefly,
179 each sample (3-4 g) was homogenized with activated sodium sulphate until a fine
180 powder was obtained and then the mixtures were introduced into previously cleaned
181 cellulose cartridges (6 h in Soxhlet). These mixtures were Soxhlet-extracted with 100
182 mL of *n*-hexane-dichloromethane (4:1 v/v) for 6 h. At this step, TBB and PCB 209 were
183 added as recovery standards (50 ng/mL). The extract was concentrated with a rotary
184 evaporator to 2 mL. Three mL of sulphuric acid were then added. After vigorous stirring
185 in a Vortex-mixer (2 min), the mixture was centrifuged (4000 rpm, 5 min) to remove
186 any foam in the interface and the sulphuric acid layer was discarded. This clean-up step
187 was repeated until a colorless transparent acid layer was obtained (3-5 times). The
188 solvent layer was introduced into a chromatographic column packed with 1 gr of
189 sodium sulphate and silica gel (1:1 by weight). The extract was then evaporated to

190 dryness under a gentle stream of nitrogen (10-20°C) and transferred to vials using 200
191 µl of isooctane. Before instrumental analysis, the sample was evaporated to nearly
192 dryness under a gentle nitrogen flow and a solution of PCB 142 was added as internal
193 standard (10 ng/mL).

194 Cheese and eggs samples were extracted following previous analytical methods,
195 with some minor modifications (Kalantzi et al., 2001). Briefly, each sample (1-2 g) was
196 homogenized with activated sodium sulphate (5 g) and then Soxhlet extracted with 50
197 mL of *n*-hexane. After cooling, the extract was spiked with TBB and PCB 209 as
198 recovery standards (50 ng/mL) and concentrated with a rotary evaporator to 5 mL. The
199 sample was then introduced into a 1.9 cm i.d. column containing 15 g of acidified silica
200 gel (2:1 silica gel:acid by weight) and eluted with 60 mL of *n*-hexane. The extract was
201 then evaporated to 1 mL under a gentle stream of nitrogen and introduced into a 0.6 cm
202 i.d. column containing 3 g of activated silica. The sample was eluted with 33 mL of
203 hexane (for PCBs) and 15 mL of hexane-dichloromethane (1:1 v/v; for OC pesticides).
204 Before instrumental analysis, the sample was evaporated to nearly dryness under
205 nitrogen and a solution of PCB 142 was added as internal standard (10 ng/mL).

206 For Hg determination each sample (5 g) was freeze-dried for 12 h and then
207 introduced (0.1 g) into a digestion Teflon vessel, together with 3 mL of nitric acid and 1
208 mL of hydrogen peroxide. The mixture was heated in an oven (90°C) overnight. After
209 cooling, the digested sample was dissolved with 40 mL of MilliQ water. Finally,
210 samples were placed in 7 mL glass bottles and stored in a refrigerator until instrumental
211 analysis.

212

213 2.5. *Determination of persistent pollutants and quality assurance*

214 The OCs were quantified using a gas chromatograph with electron capture detection
215 (GC-ECD, Agilent Technologies 7890A, Palo Alto, California, USA) equipped with a
216 HP-5MS capillary column of 60 m length, 0.25 mm internal diameter and 0.25 µm film
217 thickness (J&W Scientific, Folsom, CA, USA), protected with a retention gap. The oven
218 temperature was programmed from 90°C (holding time 2 min) to 130°C at 15°C/min
219 and finally to 290°C at 4°C/min, keeping the final temperature for 15 min. Injector and
220 detector temperatures were 250°C and 320°C, respectively. Injection (2 µl) was
221 performed in the splitless mode, keeping the split valve closed for 30 s. Helium was the
222 carrier gas (1.5 mL/min) and nitrogen was used as make-up gas (60 mL/min).

223 Structural confirmations were performed by GC (Agilent Technologies 7890A,
224Agilent Palo Alto, USA) coupled to mass spectrometry (MS, Agilent Technologies
2255975C, Agilent Palo Alto, USA) operating in negative chemical ionization mode (GC-
226NICI-MS). The system was equipped with a HP-5MS capillary column of 60 m length,
2270.25 mm internal diameter and 0.25 μm film thickness (J&W Scientific, Folsom, CA,
228USA), protected with a retention gap. Helium was used as carrier gas (1.2 mL/min).
229Ammonia was the reagent gas (2.5 mL/min). The oven temperature program started at
23090°C which was held for 2 min, followed by a first increase to 130°C at 15°C/min and a
231final ramp to 310°C at 4°C/min with a final holding time of 10 min. Injector, transfer
232line and ion source temperatures were 280°C, 280°C and 176°C, respectively. The dwell
233time was 100 ms/channel.

234 One procedural blank was included in each batch of samples. Mean recoveries of
235spiked standards in the samples were 55% and 75% for TBB and PCB 209, respectively.
236Detection and quantification limits were determined as the average signal obtained from
237the blanks plus three and five times the standard deviation, respectively. Detection limits
238ranged between 0.0050 and 0.095 ng/g wet weight.

239 Total Hg was performed using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
240(ICP-MS, Elan 6000) operating under standard conditions and using rhodium as internal
241standard. One procedural blank was included in each sample batch. The detection limit
242was 0.00010 mg/kg wet weight. Analyses of fish muscle certified reference material,
243ERM-BB422, containing 0.601 ± 0.03 mg/kg of Hg ensured that the instrument
244remained calibrated along the study. The mean recovery obtained was 94%.

245

2462.6. *Dietary exposure estimates*

247The estimation of the daily intake of pollutants through the consumption of selected
248food items was calculated by multiplying the mean pollutant concentration in the item
249(expressed in ng/g fresh product) by the average daily consumption rate of that item
250(expressed in grams/day). Then, total dietary intake was obtained by summing these
251products for each contaminant.

252 The daily consumption rates of the 4-year old children living in Menorca were
253obtained by combining the information from the FFQs (expressed in times/week) and
254the servings of each food item at the age of 4 years as defined by AESAN (expressed in
255grams; vegetables = 130 g, meat = 53 g, shellfish = 73 g, fish = 73 g, eggs = 50 g,

256cheese = 27 g and fruit = 87 g). The FFQs from INMA-Menorca were based on a
257representative sample encompassing 302 children (average body weight = 18.5 kg).

258

2592.7. *Statistical analysis*

260The statistical analyses were performed using R (R Core Team, 2015) software and
261Microsoft Excel (2010). The concentrations of OCs and Hg were expressed in ng/g wet
262weight (ww) and mg/kg wet weight, respectively. When OCs and Hg concentrations
263were under the limit of detection, the values were assumed to be one-half of the
264detection limits (ND= $\frac{1}{2}$ LOD). Either ww or dry weight (dw) were used for comparison
265with other studies.

266 Total HCHs were defined from the sum of α -, β - and γ -HCHs. Total DDT
267concentrations were the sum of 4,4'-DDT, 2,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE, 2,4'-DDE and 4,4'-
268DDD. Total PCB concentrations were the sum of 28, 52, 118, 138, 153 and 180. HCB
269and Hg were reported as individual compounds.

270 Serum OCs and hair Hg concentrations (Carrizo et al., 2006; Gari et al., 2013)
271were not normally distributed and were transformed into natural logarithms.
272Multivariate linear regression analyses were used to assess the association of children's
273dietary intakes and other covariates (sex, place of birth, breastfeeding, number of
274siblings, maternal age, and maternal and paternal occupation and educational level),
275with each compound concentration at 4-year old children. The compound
276concentrations and food item variables included in the models were standardized.

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278

2793. **Results**

280The descriptive data of the OC and Hg concentrations in the analysed foodstuffs are
281shown in Tables 1-3. Non-detected compounds (e.g. PeCB, β - and γ -HCH) or
282compounds presenting low detection frequencies (e.g. α -HCH, δ -HCH, 2,4'-DDT,
283PCB28 and PCB52) were not reported. The relative distributions of the main pollutant
284groups (HCB, Σ HCHs, Σ DDTs, Σ PCBs and Hg) to the total sum of persistent
285pollutants (Σ PP) are shown in Fig. 2.

286

2873.1 *Fish and shellfish*

288All fish and seafood samples showed detectable levels of 4,4'-DDE and PCB congeners
289118, 138, 153 and 180 (Tables 1 and 2). 4,4'-DDT and 4,4'-DDD were found in 87%

290 and 57% of the analysed samples, respectively. The other major compounds, e.g. HCB
291 and 2,4'-DDE, were found in 50% of the samples (Tables 1 and 2). The patterns of
292 DDTs and PCBs in fish and seafood were dominated by 4,4'-DDE and PCB153. The
293 highest OC concentration in fish was found in European hake (6.1 ng/g ww of 4,4'-
294 DDE). The highest concentration in shellfish was observed in mussel (1.8 ng/g ww of
295 PCB153). These two samples were collected in Maó (Tables 1 and 2).

296 All fish and shellfish samples showed detectable Hg levels, ranging between
297 0.068 and 3.8 mg/kg ww (arithmetic means of 1.1 mg/kg ww and 0.92 mg/kg ww for
298 fish and shellfish, respectively; Tables 1 and 2).

299 Small-spotted catshark caught in Ciutadella was the species showing highest
300 concentrations within the seafood group (3.8 mg/kg ww; Table 1). As shown in Fig. 2
301 Hg was the major persistent pollutant in fish and shellfish, contributing 99% to the total
302 load.

303

304 3.2 Meat

305 All samples showed detectable levels of 2,4'-DDE, 4,4'-DDD, PCB118, PCB138 and
306 PCB153 (Table 2). The other compounds, e.g. HCB, 4,4'-DDT and 4,4'-DDE, were
307 found in less than 60% of the samples and PCB180 was not found in any. The DDT and
308 PCB patterns were mostly dominated by 4,4'-DDE and PCB118, respectively. The
309 highest concentrations were found in lamb bought in Ciutadella (0.26 ng/g ww of 4,4'-
310 DDE; Table 2).

311 Hg was also the major persistent pollutant in the meat foodstuff group,
312 contributing to 98 % of Σ PP (Fig 2). However, it was only found in beef and lamb
313 samples from Maó (Table 2).

314

315 3.3. Fruit and vegetables

316 All fruits and vegetables showed detectable levels of 2,4'-DDE, 4,4'-DDD, PCB118,
317 PCB138 and PCB153 (Table 3). PCB180 was found in half of the analysed vegetable
318 samples but not in any of the fruits. HCB, 4,4'-DDT and 4,4'-DDE were not found in
319 any of the fruit or vegetable samples. The DDT and PCB patterns were dominated by
320 2,4'-DDE and PCB138 in most of the samples from both groups. The highest OC
321 concentrations found in fruit and vegetables corresponded to PCB138, 0.13 and 0.22
322 ng/g ww, respectively. Hg was not found above detection limit in any sample (Table 3).

323 The PCBs were the major persistent pollutants in both groups of fruit and
324vegetables followed by DDTs (Fig 2). In the fruit group, PCBs and DDTs constituted
32555% and 18% of the Σ PP, respectively. In the vegetables, these pollutants represented
32667% and 15% of Σ PP, respectively.

327

3283.4 Cheese

329All samples contained 4,4'-DDT, PCB138, PCB153 and PCB180 above limit of
330detection (Table 3). PCB118 was found in 67% of the samples. HCB, 4,4'-DDE, 2,4'-
331DDE and 4,4'-DDD were below limit of detection in all cases. The DDT and PCB
332patterns were dominated by PCB138 and 4,4'-DDT, respectively. The highest
333concentration was found in cheese from Maó (0.3 ng/g ww of PCB138).

334 Hg was found above limit of detection in all samples, ranging between 0.097 and
3350.24 mg/kg ww (arithmetic mean 0.16 mg/kg ww). The semicured cheese from Maó
336showed the highest level (0.24 mg/kg ww; Table 3). This metal was the major persistent
337pollutant in the cheese group, with a similar relative composition as observed in fish and
338shellfish (Fig. 2).

339

3403.5 Eggs

3414,4'-DDT was found in all analysed egg samples (Table 3). PCB118, PCB138, PCB153
342and PCB180 were found in 50% of the samples. The PCB and DDT patterns were
343dominated by PCB153 and 4,4'-DDT, respectively. The highest OC concentrations were
344found in chicken eggs from Maó (0.24 ng/g ww of PCB153). PCBs and DDTs were the
345major persistent pollutant in this group (Fig 2), contributing to 62% and 15% to Σ PP,
346respectively. No Hg was found above limit of detection (Table 3).

347

3483.6 Human biomonitoring

349Hair Hg and serum OC concentrations from the studied infant population of Menorca
350are shown in Table 6. THg concentrations in hair ranged from 0.040 ug/g to 10 ug/g,
351with a geometric mean (GM) concentration of 0.99 ug/g (Garí et al., 2013), which
352represents 20% of the samples that were above the WHO recommended values in
353human hair. Concerning OCs, the most abundant was 4,4'-DDE, with a GM
354concentration of 0.87 ng/ml, followed by sum of PCBs (0.63 ng/ml), HCB (0.22 ng/ml)
355and 4,4'-DDT (0.069 ng/ml) (Carrizo et al., 2006).

356

3574. Discussion

358

3594.1 Occurrence of OCs in food items

360The concentrations of OCs were considerably higher in fish and shellfish than in the
361other food groups (Tables 1-3) which is consistent with studies from other European
362countries, e.g. Sweden (Törnkvist et al., 2011). Fruits and vegetables showed the lowest
363concentrations of these pollutants.

364 The PCB congeners found in highest concentrations in all samples were those
365with highest molecular weights, PCB118, PCB138, PCB153 and PCB180, which
366involves those with highest hydrophobic properties (octanol-water coefficients, $\log K_{ow}$
367> 6.9). The predominance of these compounds is consistent with their high
368hydrophobicity and bioaccumulation potential. 4,4'-DDE was the compound of the
369DDT group showing highest concentrations. The DDT/DDE ratios were low in all food
370samples, ranging between 0.013 and 1.2, which is indicative of old DDT exposure.

371 In general terms, the observed concentrations of HCB, total HCHs and total
372DDTs in meat, fruits, vegetables, eggs, cheese and dairy products from the island were
373low in comparison to those found in previous studies from other European regions, e.g.
374Croatia (Kljakovic-Gaspic et al., 2015), Austria (Mihats el al., 2015), Sweden
375(Törnkvist et al., 2011), Catalonia (Martí-Cid et al., 2010; Falcó et al., 2004; Llobet et
376al., 2003a) and Russia (Polder et al., 2010; Table 4). The concentrations of PCBs in the
377food items from the island were in the range of those described elsewhere although the
378number of cases for comparison was small (Table 4).

379 Concerning fish and seafood, the concentrations of HCB, total HCHs, DDTs and
380PCBs in the specimens captured nearby the island were small in comparison to the fish
381specimens consumed in these other European countries (Table 4). With a few
382exceptions, HCB from Sweden (Törnkvist et al., 2011) and DDTs and PCBs from the
383Canary Islands (Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2016), the average concentrations of fish
384and seafood from Menorca were the lowest observed (Table 4). The differences were
385particularly significant for the DDT and the PCB groups since the average
386concentrations found in the fish/seafood group of Menorca were about 6-7 times lower
387than the average concentrations reported in Catalonia (Martí-Cid et al., 2010; Llobet et
388al., 2003a) or Russia (Polder et al., 2010) (Table 4). In general, decreasing

389 concentrations in OCs have been observed (Krauthacker et al., 2009; Aguilar et al.,
390 2005), probably as the result from the application of the Stockholm Convention.

391 The highest OCs concentrations were observed in the European hake from Maó
392 (Σ OCs=11 ng/g ww; Table 1). This is a carnivore species that feeds on small fish and
393 certain cephalopods, thus occupying a high level in the food chain. As mentioned above,
394 most OCs are hydrophobic and have high $\log K_{ow}$ coefficients which increases their
395 affinity for specimens with high fat content and for those located at high position in the
396 food web. Accordingly, the lower OC levels in shellfish than fish (Tables 1 and 2) can
397 be related to their lower fat content.

398 PCBs were the OCs found in highest concentrations in the meat samples, 0.43
399 ng/g ww (Table 4), followed by DDTs (0.15 ng/g ww), HCB (0.028 ng/g ww) and
400 HCHs (<0.033 ng/g ww). The beef and lamb showed higher levels than chicken,
401 probably due to the mammalian transference of these compounds through placenta and
402 by breast feeding (Table 2; Shen et al., 2004).

403 Semicured cheese samples containing 15% fat showed lower OCs levels than
404 semicured cheese with higher fat content (Table 3). The concentrations of these
405 compounds in cheese and eggs from Menorca were lower than those found in Russia
406 (Polder et al., 2010) and similar to those found in Catalonia (Llobet et al., 2003a; Table
407 4).

408 Finally, the fruit and vegetables analyzed in the present study showed the lowest
409 OC concentrations which is consistent with the observed accumulation of these
410 compounds in Catalonia (Martí-Cid et al., 2010; Falcó et al., 2004) and Russia (Polder
411 et al., 2010; Table 2). This low accumulation pattern was not unexpected as these food
412 items are in a low position of the food chain and their fat content is also low.

413

414 4.2 Occurrence of Hg in food items

415 Hg was present in all fish, shellfish and cheese samples and in 40 % of the meat
416 samples. In contrast, it was not found in fruit, vegetables and eggs items (Tables 1-3).
417 The highest Hg concentrations were found in seafood, ranging between 0.068 and 3.8
418 mg/kg ww. Sixty-six percent of the analysed species had Hg concentrations above the
419 maximum level set forth by the European Union Maximum Residue Limits (MRL) for
420 human consumption, 0.5-1.0 mg/kg ww depending on the species (EC, 2006).

421 The Hg concentrations observed in the present study were consistent with
422 previous results reported in the same organisms from the Adriatic Sea (Storelli and

423Barone, 2013; Storelli et al., 2003), Farwa Island (Lybian coast; Banana et al., 2016),
424the Gulf of Lion (Torres et al., 2015; Cresson et al., 2014), the Aegean Sea (Yabanli et
425al., 2015) and deep-sea sites from the Mediterranean basin (Koenig et al., 2013; Naccari
426et al., 2015).

427 A considerable variation was found in Hg concentrations among species. Biotic
428and abiotic factors may affect the accumulation of Hg in marine organisms. However,
429diet and position in the trophic web are determinant (Storelli et al., 2002).

430 The highest concentration was measured in small-spotted catshark collected in
431Ciudadella (average 3.8 mg/kg ww; maximum 14 mg/kg dw). In a recent study in fish
432from the Gulf of Lions (Northern Mediterranean), the same species recorded maximum
433average values, with an arithmetic mean of 7.1 mg/kg dw, and maximum concentration
434of 27 mg/kg dw (Cresson et al., 2014). In another study in the Mediterranean basin
435lower concentrations were observed (arithmetic mean 1.5 mg/kg ww, range 0.79-2.6
436mg/kg ww; Storelli et al., 2002).

437 Small-spotted catshark is a predator with a diet mainly based on consumption of
438osteichthyes and crustaceans, cephalopods and gastropods. Its trophic level is high
439(3.93) since it is a top carnivorous predator (Mnasri et al., 2012). The observed high Hg
440concentrations are consistent with magnification processes due to their high trophic
441position and feeding behavior.

442 Concerning shellfish, the highest concentrations were recorded in shrimp from
443Maó (average 2.3 mg/kg ww). These results were in concordance with a previous study
444in the Mediterranean basin, with arithmetic mean and the maximum levels of 1.0 and
4452.2 mg/kg ww, respectively (Koenig et al., 2013).

446 Semi-cured cheese was the second food group with highest average Hg
447concentrations (0.16 mg/kg ww) followed by meat (0.040 mg/kg ww; Table 1). Cheese
448with low fat content (15%) was the food item with lowest Hg concentration (0.097
449mg/kg ww), which parallels the observations on OC concentrations. The Hg
450concentrations in these food items were higher than those found in other studies in the
451Canary Islands (Rubio et al., 2008) and Catalonia (Llobet et al., 2003b).

452

4534.3 Dietary intake of OCs and Hg

454The contributions of each food group to the total dietary intake of OCs and Hg in the
455cohort of four-year old children from Menorca are shown in Fig. 3. The most important
456OC sources were consumption of fish (37%) and fruit (29%). However, it is important

457to note the significant differences among consumption rates of these food items: 107
458g/day in fruit and 20.2 g/day in fish (Table 5) involving 47 ng/d and 64 ng/d,
459respectively. The high significance of the fish contribution to the total dietary OC intake
460has also been observed in previous studies from other European populations (Mihats et
461al., 2015; Törnkvist et al.; 2011, Llobet et al., 2003a). Vegetables and shellfish were also
462identified as important contributors to the OC estimated daily intakes (EDIs; 13% and
4637%, respectively).

464 Further understanding on the significance of each food item for the OC intake
465can be obtained by consideration of the Tolerable Daily Intakes (TDIs; JMPR, 2000).
466According to the results of the present study, the EDIs of OCs of the 4 year-old children
467from Menorca are much lower than the established TDI limits (TDI for HCB=160 ng/
468(kg bw·d), for Σ HCHs=5000 ng/(kg bw·d), for Σ DDTs=10,000 ng/(kg bw·d), for
469 Σ PCBs=10 ng/(kg bw·d); Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2016; JMPR, 2000; Mihats et al.,
4702015).

471 However, in comparison with previous studies, the PCBs EDIs of 4-year old
472children from Menorca was higher than children ingestion (6-15 years old) from Austria
473(Σ PCBs=3.37 ng kg⁻¹bw d⁻¹; Mihats et al., 2015). Focussing only on fish products, a
474recent study in children (average body weight=34.32 kg) from the Canary Islands found
475higher levels than those from the present study (Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2016).

476 Fish and shellfish were the main contributors to the total Hg intake (76% and
47717% of contribution, respectively). Because of its toxicity, the EFSA's CONTAM Panel
478established a Provisional Tolerable Weekly Intake (PTWI) of 4 µg/kg for this metal
479(EFSA, 2012). According to the present results, children from Menorca Island showed
480an estimated weekly intake (EWI) of 11 µg/kg, which exceeded more than twice the
481PTWI limits. This value represents the worst scenario, and taking into account that total
482consumption of fish and seafood is from local origin. The Menorca population also
483consumes fish and seafood from other Mediterranean areas, as well as from the Atlantic
484Ocean, and the consumption from local sites is supposed to be less than half of the total.
485The worst case scenario of a study in baby foods from the European Union market
486encompassed an EWI of 18.2 µg/kg in infants (7-8 months old) whose diet consisted on
487infant formulae of milk-based and fish-based infant solid foods (Pandelova et al., 2012).
488A study in women (25-44 years old) from Spain has shown that the Hg EWI largely
489exceeds the PTWI for methylHg as consequence of consumption of sword-fish and
490louvar (Herreros et al., 2008).

491 The specific fish and seafood EDI of Menorca (Mediterranean Sea) can be
492 compared with one from the Canary Islands (Atlantic Ocean) based on the results
493 reported in Rodriguez-Hernandez et al. (2016) from children having average body
494 weight of 34.32 kg. The EDI identified in this case, 150 ng/(kg bw·d), is nearly ten
495 times lower than 1500 ng/(kg bw·d) that was observed in the four-year old children
496 from Menorca (Table 5).

497

498 4.4 Associations between pollutant concentrations in children and dietary intakes

499 The present dietary food analyses can be related to the hair Hg measurements in four-
500 year old children from Menorca (Garí et al., 2013). The infant Hg concentrations show a
501 positive and significant association with the fish and shellfish intake (Fig 4). This result
502 is consistent with those obtained in a previous study in which the contribution of each
503 food source to Hg intake was estimated from FFQs (Garí et al., 2013). The high Hg
504 concentrations found in the analysed marine organisms (Table 1) and the dietary intake
505 estimations show that 93% of the total dietary Hg intake originates from seafood
506 consumption (Fig 3). Fish intake is highly beneficial although consumption of some
507 kind of fishes such as dusky grouper and small-spotted catshark should be restricted
508 during infancy.

509 There is also a significant dependence between the intake of 4,4'-DDT and fish
510 and meat consumption (Fig. 4). Meat intakes were also found to be associated with
511 DDT concentrations in another Mediterranean area (Valencia; Llop et al., 2010). In the
512 analysed food items of Menorca, 87% of fish samples and 60% of meat samples
513 presented detectable values for 4,4'-DDT. Moreover, egg intake is also related to high
514 4,4'-DDT levels, although without statistical significance (Fig. 4). All analysed chicken
515 eggs samples showed detectable 4,4'-DDT levels.

516 The significant negative relationship between higher consumption of vegetables
517 and concentrations of PCB138, PCB153 and PCB180, or fruit and concentrations of
518 4,4'-DDT in children suggests that high intake of these food items could be associated
519 to lower consumption rates of other products, such as fish and meat, where PCBs and
520 DDT tend to accumulate strongly (Fig. 4). As a result, lower intake of PCBs and DDT
521 is observed. In this respect, PCB concentrations in the vegetable samples were above
522 the limit of detection, and 4,4'-DDT was not found in any of the fruit samples
523 analyzed. This last results is, however, not statistically significant.

524

525

5265. **Conclusions**

527

528In general terms, the concentrations of HCB, HCHs and DDTs in the food items
529produced in Menorca are low in comparison with other studies from other European
530regions. The concentrations of PCBs are in the range of those found in other European
531sites. However, the fish specimens from Menorca showed much lower PCB
532concentrations.

533 In contrast, Hg was present in all fish, shellfish and cheese samples and in 40 %
534of the meat samples of Menorca. However, it was not found in fruit, vegetables and
535eggs. Sixty-six percent of the analysed fish species had Hg concentrations above the
536maximum level set forth by the European Union MRL for human consumption.

537 The highest OC and Hg concentrations were observed in fish, presenting the
538maximum values in European hake and small-spotted catshark, respectively. These two
539species occupy high levels in the food chain where magnification processes are
540strongest for hydrophobic compounds with high bioaccumulation potential.

541 The most important sources for the intake of OCs in four-year old children from
542Menorca were consumption of fish (37%) and fruit (29%). However, the EDIs of these
543pollutants were low in comparison to the FAO/WHO TDIs. Fish (76%) and shellfish
544(17%) consumption were the main Hg sources. In the worst scenario, and assuming that
545total fish and seafood consumption is from local origin, the EWI of this metal in
546children from Menorca exceeded more than twice the EFSA PTWI.

547 A statistically significant and positive association was found between fish and
548shellfish consumption and hair Hg concentrations in 4 year-old children. Ninety-three
549percent of all dietary Hg intake originated from consumption of these food items. 4,4-
550DDT intake was also significantly directly associated to consumption of fish and meat.
551Hg and 4,4'-DDT are the only pollutants whose concentrations in children from the
552cohort were significantly associated to dietary inputs. Consumption of vegetables was
553protective against PCB accumulation.

554

555

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557

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561

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749**Table 1** OCs (ng/g wet weight) and Hg (mg/kg wet weight) in fish from markets of Menorca.

	Site of purchase	HCB	4,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDE	2,4'-DDE	4,4'-DDD	PCB118	PCB138	PCB153	PCB180	DDT/DDE	Hg
Detection Frequency (%)		52%	87%	100%	48%	57%	100%	100%	100%	100%		100%
Angler	Ciudadella	0.049	0.035	0.99	0.065	0.019	0.22	0.42	0.55	0.18	0.035	0.27
Angler	Maó	0.014	0.055	0.57	0.0064	0.0039	0.15	0.26	0.50	0.18	0.095	0.62
Black seabream	Ciudadella	0.014	0.031	0.39	0.010	0.0039	0.27	0.40	0.50	0.15	0.080	0.11
Black seabream	Ciudadella	0.019	0.010	0.79	0.037	0.0039	0.19	0.35	0.38	0.14	0.013	0.76
Black seabream	Maó	0.014	0.043	0.42	0.0064	0.0025	0.18	0.29	0.35	0.12	0.10	0.98
Common dentex	Maó	0.014	0.21	2.1	0.0064	0.017	0.36	0.94	1.3	0.42	0.10	2.0
Common pandora	Ciudadella	0.014	0.0079	0.15	0.047	0.011	0.18	0.24	0.25	0.076	0.054	0.16
Common seabream	Maó	0.083	0.071	0.95	0.0064	0.0025	0.27	0.50	0.77	0.22	0.075	0.69
Dusky grouper	Maó	0.014	0.039	0.54	0.0064	0.0025	0.25	0.49	0.64	0.28	0.071	2.5
European hake	Ciudadella	0.15	0.13	3.9	0.050	0.062	0.37	0.95	1.0	0.47	0.033	1.2
European hake	Maó	0.15	0.40	6.1	0.086	0.15	0.50	1.4	1.8	0.69	0.064	0.56
Forkbeard	Ciudadella	0.37	0.056	2.1	0.047	0.025	0.26	0.53	0.68	0.29	0.026	1.0
Forkbeard	Maó	0.28	0.090	1.7	0.0064	0.0025	0.32	0.64	0.87	0.37	0.052	1.4
Mediterranean moray	Maó	0.014	0.038	0.38	0.0064	0.0025	0.19	0.33	0.46	0.19	0.10	1.1
Red mullet	Ciudadella	0.014	0.010	0.26	0.040	0.0039	0.13	0.20	0.20	0.057	0.040	0.17
Red scorpionfish	Ciudadella	0.019	0.021	0.24	0.056	0.0079	0.27	0.52	0.72	0.26	0.088	1.4
Red scorpionfish	Maó	0.019	0.0079	0.57	0.0064	0.0025	0.17	0.33	0.50	0.17	0.014	0.42
Red sea bream	Ciudadella	0.019	0.033	0.36	0.045	0.0097	0.19	0.30	0.34	0.12	0.091	0.21
Small-spotted catshark	Ciudadella	0.014	0.12	2.3	0.0064	0.0025	0.47	1.6	1.3	1.1	0.050	3.8
Small-spotted catshark	Maó	0.014	0.035	0.36	0.0064	0.0025	0.19	0.36	0.50	0.16	0.095	1.1
Surmullet	Maó	0.044	0.040	0.23	0.0064	0.0025	0.16	0.23	0.26	0.073	0.17	0.39
Thornback ray	Ciudadella	0.014	0.0079	0.54	0.039	0.0039	0.20	0.33	0.37	0.17	0.015	1.7
Thornback ray	Maó	0.054	0.028	0.59	0.0064	0.0025	0.25	0.33	0.54	0.25	0.047	2.1
Mean		0.061	0.066	1.2	0.026	0.015	0.25	0.52	0.65	0.27	0.066	1.1
Min		0.014	0.0079	0.15	0.0064	0.0025	0.13	0.20	0.20	0.057	0.013	0.11
Max		0.37	0.40	6.1	0.086	0.15	0.50	1.6	1.8	1.1	0.17	3.8

751 **Table 2** OCs (ng/g wet weight) and Hg (mg/kg wet weight) in seafood and meat from markets of Menorca.

	Site of purchase	HCB	4,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDE	2,4'-DDE	4,4'-DDD	PCB118	PCB138	PCB153	PCB180	DDT/DDE	Hg
Shellfish												
Detection Frequencies (%)		43%	86%	100%	57%	57%	100%	100%	100%	100%		100%
Mussel	Maó	0.014	0.15	0.33	0.060	0.029	1.1	1.2	1.8	0.17	0.44	0.068
Scampi	Ciudadella	0.019	0.033	0.71	0.062	0.0089	0.26	0.35	0.40	0.15	0.046	0.74
Scampi	Maó	0.014	0.028	0.29	0.0064	0.0025	0.16	0.22	0.21	0.060	0.097	0.77
Shrimp	Ciudadella	0.014	0.0079	0.17	0.041	0.0083	0.14	0.15	0.12	0.016	0.046	1.8
Shrimp	Maó	0.014	0.028	0.20	0.0064	0.0025	0.18	0.21	0.16	0.045	0.14	2.3
Squid	Ciudadella	0.053	0.055	0.86	0.061	0.014	0.34	0.67	0.77	0.12	0.064	0.30
Squid	Maó	0.049	0.13	0.67	0.0064	0.0025	0.29	0.63	1.0	0.31	0.19	0.36
Mean		0.025	0.062	0.47	0.035	0.0097	0.35	0.48	0.64	0.12	0.15	0.92
Min		0.014	0.0079	0.17	0.0064	0.0025	0.14	0.15	0.12	0.016	0.046	0.068
Max		0.053	0.15	0.86	0.062	0.029	1.1	1.2	1.8	0.31	0.44	2.3
Meat												
Detection Frequencies (%)		40%	60%	20%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	ND	40%
Beef	Ciudadella	0.014	0.021	0.045	0.025	0.0039	0.19	0.17	0.11	0.011	0.46	0.00010
Beef	Maó	0.014	0.022	0.045	0.038	0.0085	0.19	0.21	0.13	0.011	0.50	0.093
Chicken	Ciudadella	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.034	0.0084	0.10	0.13	0.088	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Lamb	Ciudadella	0.052	0.010	0.26	0.032	0.0082	0.12	0.060	0.0871	0.011	0.039	0.00010
Lamb	Maó	0.048	0.0079	0.045	0.027	0.0092	0.14	0.14	0.11	0.011	0.18	0.11
Mean		0.028	0.014	0.089	0.032	0.0076	0.15	0.14	0.10	0.011	0.27	0.040
Min		0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.025	0.0039	0.10	0.060	0.087	0.011	0.039	0.00010
Max		0.052	0.022	0.26	0.038	0.0092	0.19	0.21	0.13	0.011	0.50	0.11

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753 **Table 3** OCs (ng/g wet weight) and Hg (mg/kg wet weight) in fruit, vegetables, cheese and eggs from Maó (Menorca).

	HCB	4,4'-DDT	4,4'-DDE	2,4'-DDE	4,4'-DDD	PCB118	PCB138	PCB153	PCB180	DDT/DDE	Hg
Fruit											
Detection Frequencies (%)	ND	ND	ND	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	ND		ND
Apple	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.032	0.0039	0.12	0.13	0.041	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Apple	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.039	0.0039	0.12	0.13	0.041	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Apple	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.036	0.0039	0.12	0.13	0.041	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Apple	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.041	0.0039	0.10	0.060	0.041	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Mean	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.037	0.0039	0.12	0.11	0.041	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Min	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.032	0.0039	0.10	0.060	0.041	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Max	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.041	0.0039	0.12	0.13	0.041	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Vegetables											
Detection Frequencies (%)	ND	ND	ND	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	50%		ND
Courgette	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.065	0.0039	0.17	0.22	0.15	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Green bean	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.052	0.0093	0.13	0.22	0.13	0.016	0.18	0.00010
Mean	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.058	0.0066	0.15	0.22	0.14	0.014	0.18	0.00010
Min	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.052	0.0039	0.13	0.22	0.13	0.011	0.18	0.00010
Max	0.014	0.0079	0.045	0.065	0.0093	0.17	0.22	0.15	0.016	0.18	0.00010
Cheese											
Detection Frequencies (%)	ND	100%	ND	ND	ND	67%	100%	100%	100%		100%
Semicured	0.014	0.037	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.12	0.30	0.24	0.094	0.82	0.239
Semicured	0.014	0.031	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.16	0.22	0.19	0.064	0.68	0.154
Semicured 15% fat	0.014	0.024	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.04	0.21	0.15	0.068	0.53	0.0966
Mean	0.014	0.030	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.10	0.25	0.19	0.075	0.68	0.163
Min	0.014	0.024	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.04	0.21	0.15	0.064	0.53	0.0966
Max	0.014	0.037	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.16	0.30	0.24	0.094	0.82	0.239
Eggs											
Detection Frequencies (%)	ND	100%	ND	ND	ND	50%	50%	50%	50%		ND
Chicken eggs	0.014	0.054	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.20	0.19	0.24	0.016	1.2	0.00010
Chicken eggs	0.014	0.031	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.040	0.048	0.033	0.011	0.70	0.00010
Mean	0.014	0.043	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.014	0.95	0.00010
Min	0.014	0.031	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.040	0.048	0.033	0.011	0.70	0.00010
Max	0.014	0.054	0.045	0.0064	0.0025	0.20	0.19	0.24	0.016	1.2	0.00010

755**Table 4.** Arithmetic mean concentrations of OCs in food items of Menorca and in other European sites (ng/g ww).

	Fish and seafood	Meat	Fruit	Vegetables	Cheese and dairy products	Eggs	Location	Reference
HCB	0.053	0.028	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014		<i>Present study</i>
	0.33	–	–	–	–	–	Canary Islands	Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2016
	0.021	–	–	–	–	–	Croatia	Kljakovic-Gaspic et al., 2015
	0.45	0.090	–	–	0.070	0.040	Sweden	A. Törnkvist et al., 2011
	0.22	–	0.005	0.14	–	–	Catalonia	Martí-Cid et al., 2010
	0.56	0.82	–	0.020	0.603	0.38	Russia	Polder et al., 2010
	0.28	0.17	0.00093	0.0056	1.7	0.18	Catalonia	Falcó et al., 2004
∑HCHs	0.038	0.033	0.035	0.033	0.033	0.033		<i>Present study</i>
	0.13	–	–	–	–	–	Canary Islands	Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2016
	0.32	–	–	–	–	–	Croatia	Kljakovic-Gaspic et al., 2015
	0.23	0.040	–	–	0.025	0.015	Sweden	Törnkvist et al., 2011
	0.20	–	0.004	0.16	–	–	Catalonia	Martí-Cid et al., 2010
	0.28	1.1	–	0.070	1.3	0.90	Russia	Polder et al., 2010
∑DDTs	1.1	0.15	0.098	0.12	0.088	0.10		<i>Present study</i>
	0.77	–	–	–	–	–	Canary Islands	Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2016
	2.8	–	–	–	–	–	Croatia	Kljakovic-Gaspic et al., 2015
	3.3	0.24	–	–	0.16	0.10	Sweden	Törnkvist et al., 2011
	7.5	–	0.069	2.8	–	–	Catalonia	Martí-Cid et al., 2010
	6.4	11	–	0.11	0.81	9.7	Russia	Polder et al., 2010
∑PCBs	1.7	0.43	0.30	0.54	0.63	0.40		<i>Present study</i>
	1.3	–	–	–	–	–	Canary Islands	Rodríguez-Hernández et al., 2016
	4.3	–	–	–	–	–	Austria	Mihats et al., 2015
	11	–	–	–	–	–	Croatia	Kljakovic-Gaspic et al., 2015
	5.1	0.33	–	–	0.10	0.15	Sweden	Törnkvist et al., 2011
	11	–	0.036	0.21	–	–	Catalonia	Martí-Cid et al., 2010
	7.4	2.9	–	0.10	2.1	5.2	Russia	Polder et al., 2010
	12	0.37	0.0045	0.021	0.67	0.47	Catalonia	Llobet et al., 2003a

Table 5 Mean values of the daily intake of each food group by 4-year old children population from Menorca (ng contaminant/(infant·day (\pm standard deviation)) (average body weight = 18.5 kg).

Consumption rate	Fish (20.2 g/day)	Shellfish (5.30 g/day)	Meat (13.7 g/day)	Fruit (107 g/day)	Vegetables (30 g/day)	Cheese (7.82 g/day)	Eggs (15.1 g/day)	EWI^a ($\mu\text{g}/(\text{kg bw}\cdot\text{week})$)	EDI^b ($\text{ng}/(\text{kg bw}\cdot\text{d})$)
HCB	1.2 \pm 1.9	0.13 \pm 0.095	0.39 \pm 0.27	1.5 \pm 0.0	0.40 \pm 0.0	0.11 \pm 0.0	0.20 \pm 0.0	0.0015	0.21
ΣHCHs	0.75 \pm 0.26	0.21 \pm 0.088	0.45 \pm 0.00	3.7 \pm 0.36	0.97 \pm 0.0	0.26 \pm 0.0	0.50 \pm 0.0	0.0026	0.37
ΣDDTs	26 \pm 32	3.1 \pm 1.7	2.0 \pm 1.3	10 \pm 0.41	3.6 \pm 0.18	0.69 \pm 0.050	1.5 \pm 0.24	0.018	2.5
ΣPCBs	34 \pm 21	8.7 \pm 7.2	5.9 \pm 1.5	32 \pm 4.8	16 \pm 0.85	5.0 \pm 1.1	6.1 \pm 5.5	0.041	5.8
Hg	22000 \pm 18000	4900 \pm 4500	550 \pm 750	11 \pm 0.0	3.0 \pm 0.0	1300 \pm 560	1.5 \pm 0.0	11	1500

^aEWI: Estimated weekly intake (EFSA, 2012). ^bEDI: Estimated daily intakes (JMPR, 2000).

761Table 6. Human biomonitoring data from 4-year old children from Menorca population: OCs in serum (n=285; expressed in ng/ml) and Hg in
762hair (n=302; expressed in ug/g).

	Geometric Mean	Min	Max
HCB	0.32	0.030	4.5
4,4'-DDT	0.069	0.046	0.66
4,4'-DDE	0.87	0.041	43.9
PCB118	0.091	0.026	1.8
PCB-138	0.17	0.037	8.7
PCB-153	0.25	0.022	10.9
PCB-180	0.12	0.0091	7.2
Hg	0.99	0.040	10

763**Figure 1** Map of the Menorca Island.

764**Figure 2** Relative contributions of HCB, Σ HCHs, Σ DDTs, Σ PCBs and Hg to Σ PP in
765the food items from Menorca.

766**Figure 3** Contribution from each food group to the total dietary intake of HCB,
767 Σ HCHs, Σ DDTs, Σ PCBs and Hg in the children living in Menorca.

768**Figure 4** Associations between dietary intakes of selected items and serum OC and hair
769Hg concentrations of four year-old children. Bars represent the 95% confidence
770intervals of each beta-coefficient. The models were adjusted for child's sex, place of
771birth, number of siblings, breastfeeding, maternal age, maternal and paternal occupation
772and educational levels.